

Synthesis, characterization and electrochemical studies of mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes of 6-chloronicotinic acid and diimines[†]

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Abstract : Four new mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes involving 6-chloronicotinic acid (6-CINA) and aromatic diimines and one binary Cu^{II} complex with 5,5'-Me₂bipy have been synthesized in aqueous/nonaqueous media. Elemental analyses (Cu, C, H, N%), molar conductance, spectral (FT-IR, UV-Visible) and room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements have been used for structural characterization of these complexes. FT-IR spectra of these complexes indicate the bidentate mode of coordination through carboxylate oxygen atoms of 6-chloronicotinate anion. On the basis of these measurements the following formulae have been proposed : [Cu(6-CINA)(bipy)(H₂O)](NO₃) (1), [Cu(6-CINA)(5,5'-Me₂bipy)(ONO₂)](H₂O) (2), [Cu(6-CINA)(phen)(H₂O)](NO₃) (3), [Cu(6-CINA)(dmp)(ONO₂)](H₂O) 4 and [Cu(5,5'-Me₂bipy)₂](ClO₄)₂ (5), {where diimines = 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy); 5,5'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (5,5'-Me₂bipy); 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline (dmp)}. The observed room temperature (300 K) magnetic moments ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.70$ to 1.84 B.M.) correspond to mononuclear complexes with one unpaired electron. The distorted square-pyramidal coordination geometry around the Cu^{II} ion has been proposed in solid complexes 1-4. In DMSO and DMF solutions, these complexes possess distorted octahedral geometry due to solvent coordination. The electrochemical behaviors of these complexes have also been studied at a glassy carbon working electrode (GCE) in DMSO and DMF media containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ as the supporting electrolyte using cyclic voltammetry. The electrochemical behavior of complex 4 involving dmp as the auxiliary ligand is different from rest of the three mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complexes.

Keywords : Mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complexes, 6-chloronicotinic acid, 5,5'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine, 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

Copper is one of the important trace transition metals found in the human body and many living organisms and is involved in the redox processes of a number of biomolecules. Excess copper in the human body has been reportedly linked to serious health threats such as cellular or organ damage and Wilson's disease^{1(a,b)}. Copper is believed to be involved in both the aggregation of amyloid- β protein (A β) and generation of oxidative stress in the patient's brain, which are key characteristics of Alzheimer's disease^{2(a,d)}. Chelation therapy has been suggested as promising therapeutic strategy for this disease^{2b}. Although copper is necessary for growth and reproduction of species living in many aquatic environments, levels just slightly above the required level are toxic to various life stages of these organisms.

The design, synthesis and crystal engineering of coordination complexes continue to be quite active research field because of their enchanting structures and potential application as functional materials^{3(a-g)}. The investigations in biological importance, supramolecular chemistry, gas adsorption/separation, and the artificial nuclease activity under appropriate conditions have been well established^{4(a-e)}. On the otherhand, transition metal ions are required for life, functioning as cofactors for myriad metalloenzymes that catalyze an extraordinary diversity of biological reactions.

Pyridinemonocarboxylic acids and its derivatives constitute an important group of antihelmintics and vitamins. It is known that the some drugs act via chelation^{5a} or via the inhibition of metalloenzymes^{5b}, but little is known about modification of the activities of most drugs that are

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandey on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

potential ligands. The structures of many complexes show that with nicotinic acid (niacin or vitamin B₃) and its derivatives acting as bridging ligands through the carboxylate group and pyridyl N-atom^{5c}. 3-Chloronicotinic acid and certain of its derivatives show remarkable physiological activity^{5d}. 6-Chloronicotinic acid (6-ClNA⁻) is important building block for agrochemicals, animal food enrichment, feed additives, reduce plasma cholesterol and pharmaceuticals^{5c}. Because nicotinic and isonicotinic acids play important role in metabolism of all living cells and much interest have been directed towards their metal complexes.

Single crystal X-ray diffraction studies have been reported for polymeric complexes [Cu(bipy)(nic)(H₂O)]NO₃.2H₂O and [Cu(phen)(nic)(H₂O)₂]NO₃.2H₂O by Xu *et al.*^{6(a,b)}, [Cu(nic-N)₂(H₂O)₄] by Kenar *et al.*⁷, CuX₂.nH₂O (where X = nicotinate anion (nic), isonicotinate (isonic), 2-methylthionicotinate (2-MeSnic), 2-chloronicotinate (2-Clnic), or 2,6-dichloronicotinate (2,6-Cl₂nic); n = 0-4) by Ahuja and coworkers⁸, Cu(nic)₂^{9a}, Cu(nic)₂.4H₂O^{9b}, Cu(isonic)₂.4H₂O^{9b} and Cu(2-Clnic)₂.H₂O^{10a}. Moncol *et al.*^{10(a,b)} have also synthesized and characterized new Cu^{II} complexes [CuX₂(Et₂nia)₂(H₂O)₂] (where X = 2-MeSnic, 2-Clnic, 2,6-Cl₂nic, isonic and Et₂nia = *N,N*-dimethylnicotinamide). These complexes possess tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry. An X-ray analysis of [Cu(2-Clnic)₂(Et₂nia)₂(H₂O)₂]^{10a} featured a tetragonal-bipyramidal geometry around the central metal ion and also of [Cu₂(μ-2-Clnic)₄(H₂O)₂]^{10b}, [Cu(2,6-Clnic)(H₂O)₂]^{10b} and [Cu(5-Brnic)₂(H₂O)₂]_n^{10b} (where Brnic = 2-bromonicotinate anion) having square pyramidal geometry about Cu^{II} with CuO₄O(w) chromophore. Andruh *et al.*¹¹ have also synthesized and characterized two nano tube-like and one ladder-like Cu^{II} coordination polymers based on the nicotinate ion as a bridging ligand and 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy), 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (Me₂bipy) or dicyanamide (dca) as coligands : [1_∞Cu₂(bipy)₂(NA)₂](ClO₄)₂.H₂O, [1_∞Cu₂(Me₂bipy)₂(NA)₂](ClO₄)₂, [1_∞Cu₃(NA)₄(dca)₂(H₂O)₈].2H₂O. The nicotinate ligand bridges simultaneously three Cu^{II} ions. The carboxylate group exhibits its classical syn-syn bridging mode forming pairs of Cu^{II} ions connected through two carboxylate groups from two NA⁻ ligands. These pairs are further interconnected through the NA⁻, each of which being

coordinated to the apical position of the Cu^{II} ion from an adjacent pair. This particular coordination function of the nicotinate ligand leads to a tube-like polymer running along the crystallographic c-axis. The tubes are constructed from the Cu^{II} ions and the nicotinate ligands. The bipy ligand molecules are oriented toward the exterior of the tubes. The stereochemistry of the central metal ion is square-pyramidal. The basal plane is formed by two nitrogen atoms arising from the bipy ligands and two oxygen atoms from the carboxylate bridges, and the apical position is occupied by a nitrogen atom from the pyridyl moiety.

In the present paper, we have reported the synthesis and characterization of four new mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complexes, viz. [Cu(6-ClNA)(bipy)(H₂O)](NO₃) (1), [Cu(6-ClNA)(5,5'-Me₂bipy)(ONO₂)](H₂O) (2), [Cu(6-ClNA)(phen)(H₂O)](NO₃) (3) and [Cu(6-ClNA)(dmp)(ONO₂)](H₂O) (4) and one binary complex [Cu(5,5'-Me₂bipy)₂](ClO₄)₂ (5) involving 6-chloronicotinate anion (6-Clnic⁻) and diimines, where diimines = 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy), 5,5'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (5,5'-Me₂bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline (dmp) in aqueous-nonaqueous media using elemental analyses, molar conductance, spectral (FTIR, UV-Visible) and room temperature magnetic measurements. The electrochemical behaviours of these complexes have also been investigated in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and dimethyl formamide (DMF) containing 0.2 M sodium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte at a glassy carbon working electrode (GCE) using cyclic voltammetry.

Experimental

Materials :

Copper(II) nitrate trihydrate, copper(II) perchlorate hexahydrate, 6-chloronicotinic acid and diimines (bipy, 5,5'-Me₂bipy, phen and dmp) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. and were used as such. AnalaR grade dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), diethylether and dimethylformamide (DMF) were procured from E. Merck India Ltd. Ethyl alcohol was purchased from Bengal Chemicals, India.

Synthesis of binary and mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complexes :

To the aqueous solution (30 ml) of Cu(NO₃)₂.3H₂O or Cu(ClO₄)₂.6H₂O (for 5) (3.33 mmol), the ethanolic

solutions of 6-chloronicotinic acid (6.66 mmol in 50 ml ethyl alcohol) and appropriate diimine (3.33 mmol in 20 ml ethanol) were slowly added with constant stirring for 2 h. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 4.5 with 1.0 M aqueous sodium hydroxide and then the solution was heated over water bath for 1 h. The solution was cooled to room temperature and then it was filtered off and the filtrate was kept for crystallization at room temperature (25 °C). Blue polycrystalline complexes **1-3** and green coloured complexes **4-5** were isolated by filtration, washed with diethylether and dried inside a vacuum desiccator. Yield \approx 65–70%.

Physical measurements :

The C, H, N microanalyses were carried out at Central Drug Research Institute (CDRI), Lucknow. For each complex the C, H, N analyses were carried out twice. The FT-IR spectra were performed on Perkin-Elmer 577 FT-IR spectrophotometer from KBr pellets in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} and room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a calibrating standard. The UV-Visible spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO and DMF solutions with a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 35 spectrophotometer. The details of cyclic voltammetric measurements have already been reported elsewhere¹².

Results and discussion

The formula, formula weight, colour, m.p., elemental analyses (Cu, C, H and N%), room temperature magnetic moments and UV-Visible absorption spectral data for these complexes **1-5** are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. On the basis of experimental results (Tables 1 and 2) the following formulae **1-5** are proposed for complexes; $[\text{Cu}(6\text{-CINA})(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{NO}_3)]$ (**1**), $[\text{Cu}(6\text{-CINA})(5,5'\text{-Me}_2\text{bipy})(\text{ONO}_2)](\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (**2**), $[\text{Cu}(6\text{-CINA})(\text{phen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{NO}_3)]$ (**3**), $[\text{Cu}(6\text{-CINA})(\text{dmp})(\text{ONO}_2)](\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (**4**) and $[\text{Cu}(5,5'\text{-Me}_2\text{bipy})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**5**). The observed room temperature (300 K) magnetic moments for these complexes are in the range 1.70–1.84 B.M. (Table 1), showing that complexes are mononuclear with $S = 1/2$ spin state and indicate absence of any antiferromagnetic interaction at that temperature.

Molar conductance and IR spectra :

Molar conductance data for complexes **2** and **4** indi-

cate that they are non-electrolyte (neutral complexes) in DMSO, **1** and **3** correspond to 1 : 1 electrolyte type (monocationic complexes) while for complex **5**, the molar conductance shows that it is a 1 : 2 electrolyte type (i.e. a dicationic complex) in DMSO solutions. The room temperature magnetic moments of these complexes suggest the presence of one unpaired electron and it is believed to be indicative of mononuclear nature of these complexes. The elemental analyses (Cu, C, H and N%) also support the proposed formulae for **1-5** (Table 1).

The IR bands of complexes **1-4** are assigned on comparing with the free ligands data. The infrared spectra of these complexes exhibit characteristic strong bands at 1586, 1585, 1611 and 1595 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and at 1386, 1385, 1408 and 1381 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ stretching frequencies for **1, 2, 3** and **4**, respectively. The $\Delta\nu$ ($\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-) - \nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-)$) values (200–214 cm^{-1}) fall in the borderline of monodentate and bidentate mode of coordination of carboxylate group. However, in these complexes bidentate chelating mode of coordination of COO^- group is proposed. The presence of broad bands at 3369, 3450, 3451 and 3451 cm^{-1} in complexes **1-4**, respectively indicate the presence of water molecules. Furthermore, the peaks at 840 and 846 cm^{-1} in **1** and **3**, respectively are assigned to rocking mode of coordinated water molecules. It is important to note that the bands at 1483, 1265, 1503 and 1278 cm^{-1} in complexes **1-4** correspond to ν_{NO} stretching frequencies of unidentate ONO_2^- ion^{13(a)}. Moreover, a peak at 640 and 667 cm^{-1} in neutral complexes **2** and **4**, respectively may be assigned to pyridyl (py) vibration^{13(b)}. Complex **5** exhibit a characteristic strong band at 1095 cm^{-1} and weak band at 922 cm^{-1} corresponding to stretching vibration of ClO_4^- counter anion^{13(a)}. The weak band at 3054 and 2927 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ (aromatic) and $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ (CH_3) of 5,5'- Me_2bipy molecule. Moreover, the presence of bands of medium intensity at 1393 and 844 cm^{-1} arise from $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching vibrations of coordinated 5,5'- Me_2bipy ligand. On the basis of these results, it is therefore proposed that these complexes probably involve five coordinated distorted square-pyramidal geometry^{13(b)}, in which Cu^{II} ion is coordinated through two oxygen atoms of a bidentate chelating carboxylate group of 6-CINA⁻ anion and both the N atoms of bipy, 5,5'- Me_2bipy , phen or dmp ligand in the basal plane,

Table 1. Formula, formula weight, elemental analyses and room temperature magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of the mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes

Complex formula	Empirical formula	Formula weight	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Elemental analyses (%):				(μ_{eff}) RT (B.M.)
					Calcd. (Found)				
					Cu	C	H	N	
[Cu(6-CINA)(bipy)(H ₂ O)](NO ₃) (1)	CuC ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₆ Cl	456	Blue	178 ± 1	13.92 (13.81)	42.10 (42.27)	2.85 (3.00)	12.28 (12.23)	1.78
[Cu(6-CINA)(5,5'-Me ₂ bipy)(ONO ₂)](H ₂ O) (2)	CuC ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₆ Cl	484	Sky blue	204 ± 1	13.12 (13.24)	44.62 (44.58)	3.51 (3.46)	11.57 (11.62)	1.80
[Cu(6-CINA)(phen)(ONO ₂)](NO ₃) (3)	CuC ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₆ Cl	480	Blue	210 ± 1	13.22 (13.13)	45.0 (45.05)	2.71 (2.64)	11.67 (11.70)	1.79
[Cu(6-CINA)(dmp)(ONO ₂)](H ₂ O) (4)	CuC ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₆ Cl	508	Green	190 ± 1	12.50 (12.58)	47.24 (47.20)	3.46 (3.52)	11.02 (10.99)	1.84
[Cu(5,5'-Me ₂ bipy) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (5)	CuC ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₈ Cl ₂	630.5	Green	271 ± 1	10.07 (10.12)	45.67 (45.70)	3.80 (3.78)	8.88 (8.93)	1.82

Table 2. UV-Visible spectral data for copper(II) complexes 1-5

Complex formula	Colour of solid compound	DMSO		DMF		Transition assignments of bands
		Colour	λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ , L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Colour	λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ , L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	
[Cu(6-CINA)(bipy)(H ₂ O)](NO ₃) (1)	Blue	Blue	684 (118)	Blue	675 (140)	d-d
[Cu(6-CINA)(5,5'-Me ₂ bipy)(ONO ₂)](H ₂ O) (2)	Sky blue	Blue	679 (30)	Blue	669 (60)	d-d
[Cu(6-CINA)(phen)(H ₂ O)](NO ₃) (3)	Blue	Blue	692 (71)	Blue	687 (170)	d-d
[Cu(6-CINA)(dmp)(ONO ₂)](H ₂ O) (4)	Green	Green	800 (35) 460 (1350)	Yellowish green	770 (70) 453 (1385)	d-d Charge transfer (CT)
[Cu(5,5'-Me ₂ bipy) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (5)	Green	Blue	720 (28) 430 (242)	Greenish blue	713 (95) 432 (260)	d-d d-d + CT

while the apical position is occupied by oxygen atom of water or ONO₂⁻ group. It should be noted that Cu^{II} ion is coordinated through 4 N atoms of two 5,5'-Me₂bipy ligands in a distorted square-planar geometry in complex 5.

Electronic absorption spectra :

The UV-Visible electronic absorption spectra of these complexes in DMSO and DMF solutions showed a weak d-d band in the range 679–800 nm (Table 2), indicative of distorted octahedral coordination in solution. A strong band at 460 and 453 nm in DMSO and DMF, respectively in case of complex 4 is assigned to charge transfer (CT) transitions and at 430 and 432 nm in these two solvents for complex 5 is attributed to d-d + CT transitions. It is noteworthy that green coloured complex 4 turns yellowish-green in DMF solution while green coloured complex 5 turns blue coloured in DMSO and greenish-blue in DMF solution due to solvent coordina-

tion along the axial directions, thus resulting into distorted octahedral environment in these solvents.

Electrochemical behaviours of complexes 1-5 in DMSO/DMF solutions :

Cyclic voltammetric data for complexes 1-4 are summarized in Tables 3 and 4 and the cyclic voltammograms (CVs) are displayed in Fig. 1. The cyclic voltammograms of complex 1 in DMSO and DMF are similar, exhibiting a diffusion-controlled, quasi-reversible reduction couple attributed to Cu^{2+/+} change with formal potential, $E^{0'} \approx -37$ mV and $E^{0'} = -24$ mV, respectively with peak current ratio $I_{\text{pa}}/I_{\text{pc}} \approx 1.0$ in DMSO but < 1.0 in DMF. A plot of I_{pc} vs square root of the scan rate ($\nu^{1/2}$) gives a straight line without any intercept, showing that the redox process is diffusion-controlled. Controlled potential coulometry experiments at -130 mV in DMSO contain-

Table 3. CV data for 1 mM [Cu(6-CINA)(diimine)] mixed-ligand complexes in DMSO containing 0.2 M NaClO₄

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	E^0 (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pa}/I_{pc}	$E_{pa'}$ (mV)	$I_{pa'}$ (μ A)
[Cu(6-CINA)(bipy)(H₂O)](NO₃) (1)							
25	-90	12	-39	102	0.9		
50	-94	20	-37	114	0.9		
100	-99	27	-36	126	0.9		
200	-104	32	-36	136	0.9		
300	-106	32	-37	138	0.9		
400	-108	32	-38	140	0.9		
500	-108	32	-38	140	0.9		
[Cu(6-CINA)(5,5'-Me₂bipy)(ONO₂)](H₂O) (2)							
25	32	136	84	104	0.8		
50	32	138	85	106	0.7		
100	32	140	86	108	0.6		
200	30	140	85	110	0.6		
300	30	140	85	110	0.5		
400	30	140	85	110	0.5		
500	30	142	86	112	0.4		
[Cu(6-CINA)(phen)(H₂O)](NO₃) (3)							
10	-30	114	42	144	1.3		
25	-31	115	42	146	1.4		
50	-32	116	42	148	1.4		
100	-34	118	42	152	1.3		
200	-34	118	42	152	1.4		
300	-34	120	43	154	1.2		
400	-34	120	43	154	1.2		
500	-36	120	42	156	1.2		
[Cu(6-CINA)(dmp)(ONO₂)](H₂O) (4)							
25	271	357	314	86	0.2	601	1.1
50	264	358	311	94	0.1	608	1.5
100	252	360	306	108	0.1	620	2.0
200	242	366	304	124		634	
300	236	372	304	136		638	
400	230	374	302	144		641	
500	228	378	303	150		646	

Table 4. CV data for 1 mM [Cu(6-CINA)(diimine)] mixed-ligand complexes in DMF containing 0.2 M NaClO₄

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	E^0 (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pa}/I_{pc}	$E_{pa'}$ (mV)	$I_{pa'}$ (μ A)
[Cu(6-CINA)(bipy)(H₂O)](NO₃) (1)							
25	-86	40	-23	126	0.5		
50	-88	40	-24	128	0.5		
100	-88	40	-24	128	0.6		
200	-89	41	-24	130	0.6		
300	-89	43	-23	132	0.6		
400	-90	44	-23	134	0.6		

500	-92	46	-23	138	0.6		
[Cu(6-CINA)(5,5'-Me ₂ bipy)(ONO ₂)](H ₂ O) (2)							
25	-78	12	-33	90	0.8		
50	-80	14	-33	94	0.8		
100	-80	16	-32	96	0.8		
200	-80	18	-31	98	0.8		
300	-80	20	-30	100	0.8		
400	-80	22	-29	102	0.8		
500	-80	24	-28	104	0.8		
[Cu(6-CINA)(phen)(H ₂ O)](NO ₃) (3)							
25	-57	21	-18	78	0.3		
50	-58	24	-17	82	0.3		
100	-58	28	-15	86	0.4		
200	-62	34	-14	96	0.5		
300	-64	36	-14	100	0.6		
400	-64	36	-14	100	0.6		
500	-64	36	-14	100	0.6		
[Cu(6-CINA)(dmp)(ONO ₂)](H ₂ O) (4)							
25	260	440	350	180		633	1.8
50	253	445	349	192		646	2.6
100	246	450	348	204		658	2.6
200	240	470	355	230		671	3.4
300						672	3.9
400						677	4.1
500						681	4.4

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of complexes 2 and 4 at 100 mV s⁻¹ in DMSO containing 0.2 M NaClO₄.

ing 0.2 M NaClO₄ for 1 have shown that one electron per molecule is involved in the redox process. CV results show that the redox process involves a quasi-reversible single electron transfer without any chemical complication in DMSO while EC mechanism is followed in DMF. It may therefore, be concluded that the reduced form of complex 1 is relatively unstable in DMF as compared to that in DMSO in the time window of the CV experiments.

Cyclic voltammograms of complex 2 in DMSO and DMF are similar with formal potential $E^{0'} \approx +85$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 104$ –112 mV and peak current ratio $I_{pa}/I_{pc} < 1.0$ in DMSO and with $E^{0'} \approx -30$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 90$ –104 mV and $I_{pa}/I_{pc} < 1.0$ DMF at scan rates 25–500 mV s⁻¹. CV results suggest that the redox process involves quasi-reversible diffusion-controlled single-electron transfer reaction followed by a chemical reaction (EC mecha-

nism)¹⁴⁻¹⁶ (Tables 3 and 4). It should be noted that complex **3** in DMSO also involves a quasi-reversible, single-electron transfer reaction ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) with peak current ratio $I_{pa}/I_{pc} > 1.0$ (Table 3), clearly indicating that the reduced complex is adsorbed¹⁴⁻¹⁶ on the surface of GCE. However, in DMF it follows EC mechanism with $E^{0'} \approx -15$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 78-100$ mV and $I_{pa}/I_{pc} < 1.0$ (Table 4).

It is worthy to mention that the cyclic voltammograms of $[\text{Cu}(6\text{-ClNA})(\text{dmp})(\text{ONO}_2)] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**4**) in DMSO and DMF solutions are almost similar but differ from rest of the mixed-ligand complexes **1-3**. The forward negative scan in the potential range +1000 to -250 mV vs Ag/AgCl revealed a rather broad cathodic peak at $E_{pc} = +252$ mV (in DMSO) and +246 mV (in DMF) with their corresponding anodic peaks at $E_{pa} = +360$ and +450 mV, respectively at 100 mV s^{-1} (Tables 3 and 4). The broad peak is due to reduction of two complex species existing in DMF solution with close redox potentials. An additional second anodic peak also appeared at $E_{pa'} = +620$ and +658 mV in DMSO and DMF, respectively which is associated with the new Cu^I complex species produced due to chemical reaction of Cu^I complex species electrogenerated at c (Tables 3 and 4 and Fig. 1). These observations clearly show that a single complex species exists in both DMSO and DMF solutions and the reduction process at c follows EC mechanism¹⁴⁻¹⁶. CV results for binary complex **5** are given in Table 5. A perusal of this table clearly shows that the reduction of this complex in DMSO is easier $E^{0'} = +57$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 78-106$ mV and $I_{pa}/I_{pc} \approx 0.8$ in DMSO as compared to that in DMF medium ($E^{0'} = +45$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 116-142$ mV and $I_{pa}/I_{pc} \approx 0.8$) in the scan rate studied (Table 5).

A comparison of $E^{0'}$ values for these mixed-ligand complexes in DMSO/0.2 M NaClO_4 clearly show that the ease of reduction follows the order (Table 3) : **4** > **2** > **3** > **1**. On the otherhand in DMF/0.2 M NaClO_4 medium this order is changed : **4** > **3** > **1** > **2** (Table 4). Furthermore, a perusal of Tables 3-5 shows that the reduction of complexes **2**, **3** and **5** is easier in DMSO ($E^{0'}$ values are more positive) while for complexes **1** and **4** it is easier in DMF medium.

Table 5. CV data for 1 mM $[\text{Cu}(5,5'\text{-Me}_2\text{bipy})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ complex in DMSO and DMF containing 0.2 M NaClO_4

Scan rate (mV s^{-1})	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	$E^{0'}$ (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pa}/I_{pc}
In DMSO					
25	18	96	57	78	0.8
50	16	98	57	82	0.8
100	12	100	56	88	0.8
200	10	104	57	94	0.8
300	8	106	57	98	0.8
400	6	108	57	102	0.8
500	4	110	57	106	0.8
In DMF					
25	-12	104	46	116	0.8
50	-14	106	46	120	0.8
100	-17	107	45	124	0.8
200	-20	110	45	130	0.8
300	-22	112	45	134	0.7
400	-24	114	45	138	0.7
500	-26	116	45	142	0.7

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